

REPORT
TO THE NANTUCKET BIODIVERSITY INITIATIVE
15 September 2009

Bryophytes of Nantucket

Collections of Norton G. Miller
May and Sep 2007
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IDENTIFIED BY NORTON G. MILLER

**VOUCHER SPECIMENS IN THE BRYOPHYTE HERBARIUM, NEW YORK STATE MUSEUM (NYS), OR
IN THE FARLOW HERBARIUM, HARVARD UNIVERSITY (FH), AND CONFIRMED BY N. G. MILLER**

Study Sites

CGSNL: cemetery, northeast corner Grove Street and New Lane, Nantucket village.

DB: Donut Bog.

*EP: interdunal swales at Eel Point (NBIBP Eel Point I).

FWP: freshwater pond, northeast corner of Quaise and Polpis roads.

GF: Gardener Farm.

HF: Hidden Forest.

LSG: Loran Station grounds, southwest of Siasconset.

LSF: fen near Loran Station Tower, southwest of Siasconset.

MCB: Milestone Cranberry Bog.

MCBWS: along dirt track along west side of Milestone Cranberry Bog.

MER: Moors End Nursery.

MMAG: grounds of Maria Mitchell Association, Nantucket village.

MR: Masquetuck (Quaise) Reservation, incl. Quaise Point.

MRF: moorland Radio Facility area.

MWDB: meadow west of Donut Bog.

NLW: wetland opposite Mayhew Lane, east side of New Lane.

*NPP: northernmost Pout Pond.

NSF: Nantucket State Forest, south of Old South Road.

NV: Nantucket village, along Federal, Main, Milk, Pleasant, Vestal, and nearby streets.

PHC: Prospect Hill Cemetery, Nantucket village.

QBG: Quaker Burying Ground, Nantucket village.

SD: 'Sconset Dump.

SF: Sanford Farm, meadowland near Trots Swamp.

*SPP: southernmost Pout Pond.

*SS: Squam Swamp and associated upland.

TB: Taupawsha Bog, 0.25 mi west of upper Pout Pond.

TL: Tupancy Links.

TMWR: *Typha* marsh, east side of Wauwinet Road.

*TS: Trots Swamp, wetland east and west of trail.
WCB: Windswept Cranberry Bog.

*are Nantucket Biodiversity Inventory sites

Field work I conducted in May and September 2007 and study of specimens kept in the Farlow Herbarium of Harvard University produced collections cited in the following mosses and liverworts of Nantucket. There are additional species reported in the literature, but I have not been able to locate voucher specimens for them, including species reported by Peter W. Dunwiddie, anchored by specimens indicated as having been deposited in the biological collections of the Maria Mitchell Association. These may still be located. In response to my query to Dr. Dunwiddie about these specimens, he reported that he also kept a duplicate set but that these were lost during his move from Massachusetts to Washington State. I have checked the online bryophyte herbaria of the New York Botanical Garden and Duke University, and some Nantucket collections awaiting to be studied are at Duke. I will continue to check other bryological herbaria for additional records.

The list below is a work in progress. I will continue my field studies on Nantucket in Sep 2009, identify the resulting specimens, and, as a final project, prepare an analysis of the bryofloras of Martha's Vineyard and Nantucket. The last will be done in collaboration with my colleague Prof. George Robinson, Department of Biological Sciences, University at Albany, Albany, New York.

Two papers have been published so far as a result of my work on Nantucket. They are

Miller, N. G. 2008. *Bryum tenuisetum* and *B. violaceum*, mosses with rhizoid tubers new to New England, U.S.A. *Evansia* 25: 57–61.

Miller, N. G. 2009. Mosses adventive and naturalized in the northeastern United States: new examples and new distributional records. *Rhodora* 111: 218–230.

Pdfs of these papers are being submitted as separate files to this report.

Bryophyta (Mosses)

Amblystegium serpens (Hedw.) Schimp. in B.S.G. — MMAG (Miller 17428).

Anomodon attenuatus (Hedw.) Hüb. — NV (Miller 17447 p.p.).

Atrichum angustatum (Brid.) Bruch & Schimp. in B.S.G. — MCBWS (Miller 17471 p.p.); NV (Miller 17441); PHC (Miller 17449-8).

A. crispum (James) Sull. — SPP (Miller 17528).

A. oerstedianum (C. Müll.) Mitt. — GF (Miller 18167); NLW (Miller 17469); NSF (Miller 17545); SF (Miller 17598); SS (Miller 17524).

Aulacomnium palustre (Hedw.) Schwaegr. — GF (Miller 18153); MCB (Miller 17453 p.p.); NLW (Miller 17470); SS (Miller 17502 p.p., 17509, 17693 p.p.).

Barbula convoluta Hedw. — LSG (Miller 17621 p.p.); NV (Miller 18148).

Brachythecium acuminatum (Hedw.) Aust. — MR (Miller 17570, 17671).

B. rivulare Schimp. in B.S.G. — MR (Miller 17661, 17667); SS (Miller 17501).

B. rutabulum (Hedw.) Schimp. in B.S.G. — CGSNL (Miller 17451); PHC (Miller 17449-6, 17449-10); SS (Miller 17526).

B. salebrosum (Web. & Mohr) Schimp. in B.S.G. — MR (Miller 17576, 17672); SS (Miller 17698).

Bryhnia novae-angliae (Sull. & Lesq. in Sull.) Grout — MR (Miller 17580, 17663).

Bryoandersonia illecebra (Hedw.) Robins. — SF (Miller 17596).

Bryum argenteum Hedw. — MWDB (Miller 18186); PHC (Miller 17449-5).

B. caespiticium Hedw. — CGSNL (Miller 17452).

B. tenuisetum Limpr. — TL (Miller 17657).

B. violaceum Crundw. & Nyh. — LSG (Miller 17621 p.p.).

Callicladium haldanianum (Grev. Crum — GF (Miller 18162 p.p.); HF (Miller 18144 p.p.); MCB (Miller 17459 p.p., 17461 p.p.); MR (Miller 17571); NSF (Miller 17558, 18172); SS (Miller 17510).

Calliargon cordifolium (Hedw.) Kindb. — SS (Miller 17481, 17495).

Ceratodon purpureus (Hedw.) Brid. — NSF (Miller 17555); PHC (Miller 17449-9); QBG (Miller 17449-1).

Climacium americanum Brid. — FWP (Miller 17677); MR (Miller 17579, 17668); SS (Miller 17483, 17515); TS (Miller 17601).

Cryphaea glomerata Bruch & Schimp. ex Sull. — NV (Miller 17444).

Ctendium subrectifolium (Brid.) Buck & Allen — SF (Miller 17597).

Dichelyma capillaceum (With) Myr. — FWP (Miller 17676, 17678).

Dicranella heteromalla (Hedw.) Schimp. — MCBWS (Miller 17471 p.p.); NSF (Miller 17544).

Dicranum condensatum Hedw. — GF (Miller 18160); MRF (Miller 17543); SF (Miller 17593 p.p., 17595).

D. flagellare Hedw. — GF (Miller 18157); HF (Miller 18138 p.p.); LSF (Miller 17622 p.p., 17635 p.p.); NSF (Miller 17560); SS (Miller 17477 p.p., 17479).

D. fulvum Hook. — SS (Miller 17517).

D. montanum Hedw. — GF (Miller 18156).

D. ontariense Peters. — GF (Miller 18158); NSF (Miller 17750, 17751, 18170).

D. polysetum Sw. — GF (Miller 18159); NSF (Miller 18171).

D. scoparium Hedw. — GF (Miller 18154, 18155); LSF (Miller 17626); NSF (Miller 17557; 18168); SD (Miller 17644); SF (Miller 17594); SS (Miller 17478, 17494).

D. undulatum Brid. — LSF (Miller 17630, 17631, 17633, 17634).

Ditrichum lineare (Sw.) Lindb. — SF (Miller 17658 p.p.)

D. pallidum (Hedw.) Hampe — MCBWS (Miller 17471 p.p.); NSF (Miller 17754); PHC (Miller 17449-7); TL (Miller 17653 p.p., 17656).

Drepanocladus aduncus (Hedw.) Warnst. var. *aduncus* — MCB (Miller 17462).

D. aduncus var. *kneiffii* (Schimp. in B.S.G.) Mönk. — MR (Miller 17664); TMWR (Miller 17699).

Entodon seductrix (Hedw.) C. Müll. — MR (Miller 17567).

Fontinalis flaccida Ren. & Card. — FWP (Miller 17679); SS (Miller 17484).

Funaria flavicans Michx. — MEN (Miller 17620).

F. hygrometrica Hedw. (Sull.) Aust. — PHC (Miller 17449-4A).

Helodium paludosum — MR (Miller 17669); TS (Miller 17605, 17611 p.p.).

Herzogiella striatella (Brid.) Iwats. — MR (Miller 17572); SS (Miller 17475, 17496 p.p., 17499 p.p.).

Hygroamblystegium tenax (Hedw.) Jenn. — MMAG (Miller 17429).

Hypnum cupressiforme Hedw. var. *cupressiforme* — HF (Miller 18127); MR (Miller 17675); PHC (Miller 17449-2); SS (Miller 17506).

H. cupressiforme var. *filiforme* Brid. — HF (Miller 18141, 18144 p.p.); MR (Miller 17566); NV (Miller 17430, 17437); SS (Miller 17498, 17696).

H. imponens Hedw. — NSF (Miller 17547, 17561, 18169).

Hypnum pallescens (Hedw.) P. Beauv. — HF (Miller 18143); MR (Miller 17573); SS (Miller 17487, 17507).

Kindbergia praelonga (Hedw.) Ochyra — NV (Miller 17442, 18149); PHC (Miller 17449-4B).

Leptodictyum humile (P. Beauv.) Ochyra — GF (Miller 18166, 18167); SS (Miller 17489).

L. riparium (Hedw.) Warnst. — SS (Miller 17480, 17485 p.p.).

Leskea gracilescens Hedw. — NV (Miller 17431, 17439B).

Leucobryum albidum (Brid. ex P. Beauv.) Lindb. — GF (Miller 18163, 18164); NSF (Miller 18173); SS (17499 p.p., 17502 p.p.).

L. glaucum (Hedw.) Ångstr. in Fries — NSF (Miller 17752).

Mnium hornum Hedw. — MCB (Miller 17460); SS (Miller 17474, 17490).

Orthotrichum anomalum Hedw. — MMAG (Miller 17700).

O. pusillum Mitt. — NV (17447 p.p.).

O. sordidum Sull. & Lesq. in Aust. — NV (Miller 17435A).

O. stellatum Brid. — HF (Miller 18137); MR (Miller 7569); NV (Miller 17432 p.p., 17447 p.p., 18146); SS (Miller 17525, 17697); MMAG (Miller 17702).

Physcomitrium pyriforme (Hedw.) Hampe — MEN (Miller 17619).

Plagiomnium cuspidatum (Hedw.) T. Kop. — PHC (Miller 17449-3).

Plagiothecium laetum Schimp. in B.S.G. — NSF (Miller 17553); SS (Miller 17512).

Platygyrium repens (Brid.) Schimp. in B.S.G. — HF (Miller 18136); MR (Miller 17568, 17673); NV (Miller 17435B, 17438).

Pleuridium subulatum (Hedw.) Ragenh. — NSF (Miller 17562); TL (Miller 17653 p.p., 17655).

Pleurozium schreberi (Brid.) Mitt. — GF (Miller 18152).

Pohlia annotina var. *decipiens* Loeske — MCB (Miller 17454, 17461 p.p., 17468); NV (Miller 18147).

P. nutans (Hedw.) Lindb. — GF (Miller 18162 p.p.); MCB (Miller 17455 p.p.); NSF (Miller 17549); TL (Miller 17653 p.p.).

Polytrichum commune Hedw. var. *commune* — MCB (Miller 17464); NSF (Miller 17556, 17559); QGG (Miller 17449).

P. commune var. *perigoniale* (Michx) Hampe — Foot Pond, F. G. Floyd, 4 Jun 1906 (FH).

P. juniperinum Hedw. — NSF (Miller 17546); SF (Miller 17593 p.p.).

P. ohioense Ren. & Card. — MR (Miller 17575).

P. piliferum Hedw. — GF (Miller 18151); QBG (Miller 17448); TL (Miller 17654).

Pseudobryum cinclidioides (Hüb.) T. Kop. — MR (Miller 17670).

Pseudoscleropodium purum (Hedw.) Fleisch. in Broth. — NV (Miller 17443).

Pylaisia polyantha (Hedw.) Schimp. in B.S.G. — MR (Miller 17563); NV (Miller 17446).

Rhynchostegium serrulatum (Hedw.) Jaeg. — north end of Miacomet Pond, W. H. Sheldon, 11 Sep 1933 (FH).

Sematophyllum adnatum (Michx.) Britt. — MR (Miller 17565).

Sphagnum affine Ren. & Card. — near Sachacha Pond. ‘Sconset, Dame, Jenks, & Swan, 19 Jul 1888 (FH).

S. atlanticum Andrus — TS (Miller 17609, 17659 p.p.).

S. bartlettianum Warnst. — DB (Miller 17533 p.p., 17542 p.p.); MR (Miller 17581); SS (Miller 17519); NSF (Miller 18174).

S. compactum DC. in Lam. & DC. — LSF (Miller 17623 p.p., 17625, 17628); SD (Miller 17637 p.p., 17639, 17640, 17645 p.p., 17646, 17647).

S. cuspidatum Ehrh. ex Hoffm. — DB (Miller 18175); TS (Miller 17600, 17607); WCB (Miller 17585).

S. fallax (Klinggr.) Klinggr. — TS (Miller 17610, 17615, 17616).

S. fimbriatum Wils. in Wils. & Hook. f. — EP (Miller 17588, 17592); MCB (Miller 17456); TS (Miller 17606, 17613 p.p.); WCB (Miller 17584).

S. flavicomans (Card.) Warnst. — DB (Miller 17533 p.p., 17535 p.p., 17542 p.p., 18184 p.p. 18185).

S. fuscum (Schimp.) Klinggr. — DB (Miller 17537 p.p., 17538 p.p., 17541).

S. lescurii Sull. in Gray — MR (Miller 17577); TS (Miller 17608, 17617, 17659 p.p.); WCB

(Miller 17586).

S. magellanicum Brid. — DB (Miller 17537 p.p., 17538 p.p., 18183); HF (Miller 18125); SD (Miller 17642 p.p., 17648); SS (Miller 17523).

S. palustre L. — EP (Miller 17590); HF (Miller 18124, 18135); SS (Miller 17503); TS (Miller 17602, 17604, 17612, 17660).

S. recurvum P. Beauv — HF (Miller 18126); SS (Miller 17500); TS (Miller 17599).

S. rubellum Wils. — DB (Miller 17533 p.p., 17535 p.p., 17537 p.p., 17539, 18184 p.p.); SD (Miller 17642 p.p., 17649, 17651).

S. subsecundum Nees — near Hummock Pond, F. G. Floyd, 10 Jun 1906 (FH).

S. tenellum (Brid.) Bory — SD (Miller 17645 p.p.).

S. tenerum Sull. & Lesq. in Sull. in Gray — DB (Miller 18176); LSF (Miller 17629); EP (Miller 17589).

S. torreyanum Sull. — SS (Miller 17513, 17514).

S. trinitense C. Müll. — TB (Miller 18187, 18188, 18189); LSF (Miller 17624); SD (Miller 17652); SSP (Miller 17527, 17529, 17530, 17531); SS (Miller 17511); TS (Miller 17613).

Straminergon stramineum (Brid.) Hedenäs — TS (Miller 17603).

Tetraphis pellucida Hedw. — GF (Miller 18161, 18162 p.p.); HF (Miller 18138 p.p.).

Thelia hirtella (Hedw.) Sull. in Sull. & Lesq. — HF (Miller 18144 p.p.); NV (Miller 17436); SS (Miller 17476, 17482, 17694).

Thuidium delicatulum (Hedw.) Schimp. in B.S.G. — MR (Miller 17582, 17583); SS (Miller 17485 p.p., 17486, 17492, 17493).

Tortula muralis Hedw. — CGSNL (Miller 17450); MMAG (Miller 17701); NV (Miller 17445 p.p.).

T. papillosa Wils. in Spruce — NV (Miller 17432 p.p., 17433, 17434 p.p., 17447 p.p.).

Ulota crispa (Hedw.) Brid. — HF (Miller 18145); NV (Miller 17473); SS (Miller 17477 p.p., 17488); MR (Miller 17564).

Warnstorfia fluitans (Hedw.) Loeske — MCB (Miller 17458, 17466); MR (Miller 17578); NPP (Miller 17532); SS (Miller 17685, 17695); TS (Miller 17611 p.p., 17613 p.p.).

Marchantiophyta (Liverworts)

Bazzania trilobata (L.) S. Gray — SS (Miller 17690).

Blasia pusilla L. — MCB (Miller 17453 p.p.).

Calypogeia fissa subsp. *neogaea* Schust. — MCB (Miller 17459 p.p.); SS (Miller 17687 p.p.).

C. muelleriana (Schiffn.) K. Müll. — DB (Miller 18178 p.p.)

Cephalozia bicuspidata (L.) Dum. — MCB (Miller 17459 p.p., 17467).

C. catenulata (Hüb.) Lindb. — SS (Miller 17504A p.p., 17683, 17691 p.p.).

C. connivens (Dicks.) Lindb. — DB (Miller 17535 p.p.); SS (Miller 17687 p.p.).

C. macrostachya Kaal. — DB (Miller 18179, 18181, 18182); HF (Miller 18129, 18130 p.p., 18134, 18139, 18142 p.p.); SD (Miller 17641 p.p.); SS (Miller 17508, 17518 p.p., 17520 p.p., 17680, 7689, 17692); TS (Miller 17614).

Cephaloziella divaricata (Sm.) Schiffn. — LSF (Miller 17635 p.p.).

C. elachista (Jack) Schiffn. — DB (Miller 18178 p.p.).

C. spinigera (Lindb.) Joerg. — DB (Miller 18542 p.p.); EP (Miller 18587 p.p., 18591); LSF (Miller 17636 p.p.).

Cladopodiella francisci (Hook.) Joerg. — SD (Miller 17637 p.p.).

Frullania tamarisci subsp. *asagrayana* (Mont.) Hatt. — MR (Miller 17574).

F. eboracensis Gott. — MR (Miller 17674); NV (Miller 17434 p.p., 17439A, 17440).

Geocalyx graveolens (Schrad.) Nees — MR (Miller 17666).

Gymnocolea inflata (Huds.) Dum. — LSF (Miller 17622 p.p., 17632); SD (Miller 17641 p.p.).

Jungermannia gracillima Sm. — MCB (Miller 17455 p.p., 17465).

Kurzia pauciflora (Dicks.) Grolle — DB (Miller 17455 p.p., 17535 p.p., 17536 p.p., 17540, 17542 p.p., 18180); SD (Miller 17638 p.p., 17643 p.p.).

K. sylvatica (Evans) Grolle — MR (Miller 17662); SS (Miller 17520 p.p., 17684).

Lophocolea heterophylla (Schrad.) Dum. — HF (Miller 18133 p.p.); MCB (Miller 17457); MR (Miller 17665); NSF (Miller 17548); SS (Miller 17504B, 17505p.p.).

Lophozia bicrenata (Schmid. ex Hoffm. Dum. — SF (Miller 17658 p.p.).

L. capitata (Hook.) Macoun — EP (Miller 17587 p.p.); SD (Miller 17637 p.p.).

Marchantia polymorpha L. — MER (Miller 17618).

Mylia anomala (Hook.) S. Gray — DB (Miller 17534 p.p., 17541 p.p., 17542 p.p.); SD (Miller 17638 p.p., 17643 p.p.).

Nowellia curvifolia (Dicks.) Mitt. — HF (Miller 18130 p.p.); SS (Miller 17504A p.p.).

Odontoschisma prostratum (Sw.) Trev. — DB (Miller 17536 p.p., 18177); HF (Miller 18128); LSF (Miller 17623 p.p.); SS (Miller 17491, 17496 p.p., 17499 p.p., 17516, 17518 p.p., 17521, 17522, 17681, 17686, 17688); SD (Miller 17650).

Pallavicinia lyellii (Hook.) Carruth. — HF (Miller 18131, 18140); SS (Miller 17497, 17693 p.p.).

Pellia epiphylla (L.) Corda — MCB (Miller 17463).

Ptilidium pulcherrimum (Web.) Vainio — SS (Miller 17682).

Radula complanata (L.) Dum. — NV (Miller 17472).

Riccardia latifrons (Lindb.) Lindb. — HF (*Miller 18130 p.p., 18132 p.p., 18142 p.p.*); SS (*Miller 17691 p.p.*).

R. palmata (Hedw.) Carruth. — HF (*Miller 18132 p.p.; 18133*).

Riccia huebeneriana Lindenb. var. *sullivantii* (Aust.) Schust. — NPP (*Miller 18150*).

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